

Assessment of Preparedness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence on Business Education Learning among Colleges of Education Lecturers in South– South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated assessment of preparedness and utilization of Artificial Intelligence on business education learning among colleges of education lecturers in South-South, Nigeria. Two research questions and one hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The total population of the study was sixty lecturers was used for the study. No sample was required because of the number of lecturers involved were few. The instrument for data collection was a researchers constructed questionnaire titled, ‘preparedness and utilization of artificial intelligence on business education learning Questionnaire (PAUOAIIOBELQ. The instrument was validated by two experts, one from curriculum and instruction Department and the other from business education Department all from college of Education, Warri. The instrument was subjected to test – retest to ascertain its reliability. To achieve this, 20 copies of the instrument was administered to lecturers in college of education, Mosogar who are not part of the study but share similar characteristics with the sample of the study. The data collected was computed using the Cronbach alpha Statistic which yield 0.74 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the research question while t-test was used to test the hypothesis. The finding among others shown that lecturers were prepared to use the AI teaching/learning while school management are not yet ready to provide the necessary resources for lecturers. It was recommended from the finding that federal, state and local government and the school administrators of higher institution should make plan to provide AI resources for the lecturers, government should also create awareness to students and lecturers on the use of AI through seminar/workshops. Finally, management of institutions of higher learning should continue training and re-training for both old and new lecturers in business education for effective use of AI tools as their teaching methods.

Keywords: Teachers, preparedness, artificial intelligence, business education.

Introduction

So many years ago, no one could believe that there was going to be anything like You Tube, Facebook, Wikipedia, Google, WhatsApp, etc. But today they are the most used digital tools on earth. In this changing world, digital technology has greatly influenced our economic, social and cultural evolution of all societies. As these new forms of technologies continue to

ravage our lives and capture our youth, schools have no choice but to make room for them. In accordance with the 21st century, countries expect their teachers and students to behave as informed and responsible digital citizen (Theiry, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence the new advancement in computer systems has the capability to perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving and decision-making (IBM, 2023 in Sameera, 2024). One of the major architects in achieving educational goals and objectives is the teachers and teachers are the backbone of any educational achievement through the use of AI for the instructional delivery. Onyiorah, (2021), described teaching and learning as the bedrock of the activities in a country's educational system. This suggests that teachers must be at the center of all activities in our educational system for teaching and learning to occur. Positive changes will be brought about by the teacher. In order to implement improvement in the learning process, educators in the twenty-first century need to be familiar with contemporary technologies. The creation, dissemination, and application of knowledge – the main goals of education – are facilitated by teaching and learning. The effectiveness of the teacher in teaching and the skills acquired by the learners will determine the quality of our educational system (Gidado, Abudullahi & Adamu, 2015 in Onyiorah, 2021). Therefore, any teachers who at this dispensation rely on the traditional teaching may not be relevant in the teaching profession. Adizu and Ehidiamben, (2024) ascertained that the introduction of robots is rising on daily basis and taken rapid advancements in AI and automation are expected to have an impact in higher education. The robots have not had academic AI., but will be made an intelligent tutoring system which means that having the required experience and teaching skills are no longer enough. This means that any teacher who lacks the digital skills among some academics may make it easier for universities to look for robots as an alternative. In line with the above, it is clear that 21st century strategies for teaching need to embrace the AI. strategies. This shows that technological advancement has been carried as improvement in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, any teacher in business education lacking this technological advancement should re-direct it steps to meet the present challenges either through training or re-training.

Our educational system has a unique opportunity to grow and develop as a result of the shift to digital. Digital technologies are crucial to our youth's academic success because they give them new ways to learn, communicate, share, create, and collaborate while also bringing new life to our schools. For students to become digitally literate and knowledgeable citizens in the digital age, these resources must be utilized and integrated into the classroom. Similarly, educators must be ready for the transition to digital. Training and support for teachers and other staff in the school are required since they are part and parcel of the action plan (Thierry 2019).

In the realm of business education, the effective integration of AI is contingent upon the readiness and preparedness of business education teachers. The needs to be considered to better the readiness and preparedness of teachers is to implement AI in the classroom are teacher's attitudes towards AI, their perceived self-efficacy in using AI tools, their expectations regarding the benefits of AI usage, and their access to resources and training in AI (Ayanwale, et al., 2022). Teachers' perspectives are critical in determining the readiness and preparedness to use AI in teaching as they are vital in assessing the value and feasibility of AI implementation. In another vein, the teachers should be equipped with the necessary training and resources which is crucial for effectively implementation of AI in the classroom. The only way the successful implementation of AI technology in education can be measured, is enhancing students learning experience (Chiu & Chai, 2020; Sue et al; 2020).

Teachers play significant role in AI technology towards education and importantly enhancing students' learning experiences. However, teachers' readiness and preparedness to use AI in teaching varies. Some of the teachers have interest in and knowledge of AI, the others may feel uncertain about its implementation in the classroom (Zhao et al., 2022) Lack of formal training in AI technology in education exhibit these challenges thereby making it important to provide teachers with the necessary support and resources (Chiu & Chai 2020). Demir & Graksin, (2022) opined that students' perceptions of AI influence teachers 'readiness and preparedness for implementation of AI in the classroom. The growing influence of AI in the educational systems according Sorgo, (2020) mentioned the critical need for teachers to involve in both the design and implementation of these technologies.

Artificial Intelligence is defined according to capeland 2024 in Obue & Onwudiwe, (2024) as the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with beings. In this context, when a teacher is not there, AI can be used to offer instruction in the classroom. However, if a teacher lacks the necessary AI technology abilities to function in the classroom, the introduction of AI will result in his termination. Thus, from lectures to test supervision, teachers must be ready for it when it enters the classroom. AI is a field of computer science that develops computerized machines and intelligent machine platforms. These devices can sense, reason, plan, solve problems, produce, and manipulate objects by processing data, patterns, and models. Algorithms are used by machine to process vast amount of data that are too large for conventional computing methods to manage. Also, AI is ideal for identifying trends and patterns and for making prediction (Thierry, 2019). AI. offer personalised learning experiences and enhancing student engagement and outcomes (Tonck, 2021).

AI also allows educators to focus more on personalised teaching and student engagement (Aikanaan, 2022). Another area A.I technology can be relevant to education is the computer vision which involves making, recording and presentation of results. Since it thinks, act, and reason, like human being, it can be deployed to area where it can perform these functions with the aid of a teacher.

Business education is a vocational field that equips students with the knowledge and abilities necessary to make a substantial contribution to a country's economic growth. As a result, it is expected that a business education program would include both intellectual and practical skills that will enable the graduate to make a living in the rapidly evolving business environment of the twenty – first century (Onojetah, 2024 in Fortune & Adizu 2024). According to Ehidihamen et al. ((2024), business education is for business and about business, which is essential for both surviving and growing as an individual. Business education is the kind of education that helps students develop the values, attitudes and knowledge that business around the world require. It provides healthy literate, self-reliant citizen that would form of creating wealth for human development resulting to sustainable and national development at large (Ehidihamen et al., 2024). Tosin et al, (2022) saw business education as a programme that impact skills, attitudes, and knowledge through teaching that will make the recipient a successful career in officer and business world. In the view, Anyaeneh & Nzegwu 2015 in Tosin et al, (2022) viewed business education as education that enable the students acquire basic education that enable the students acquire basic education for teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, office understanding, office environment and vocational practices. Business educators must be prepared to us A.I technology to educate the students in this new era. Business education is a programme that provides opportunities for training for both the teachers and students in the face of modern technologies.

The teachers in the 21st century will be faced with a lot of challenges if he does not change the strategy, way and method of teaching to harness with the existing technologies to the coming one. Coping with the existing technologies new ones emerging and so he has to learn them and use them to enable him remain and relevant in the teaching profession. This was supported by Oliver, (2008) that since modern office and institutions have been transformed to e-office/e-learning process any workers/teachers who possess teaching modern technologies skills will remain relevant. Based on this, institutions and organization need to send their staff for training and re-training bearing in mind the changes in technology springing up on daily basis. Although most teachers or workers are not given the opportunity or been sponsor to go for training in order to update their knowledge.

There are many complaints that business education, which equips students with the attitude, abilities and knowledge necessary to handle complex modern office technologies is yet failing to help teachers become proficient in using these tools to offer instruction. When the AI finally arrives, these teachers might struggle to stay in the academic field. It is expected of all institutions to prepare for rainy days by retraining and educating their teachers on artificial intelligence and technology use. In order to notify institutions and others agencies about the necessity of preparing their teachers for the delivery of education by artificial intelligence, the researchers embark on the study.

Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to look at the teacher's preparedness in the use of AI in the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which lecturer's preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent to which the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhances the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study

1. To what extent does the lecturers' preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?
2. To what extent does the lecturer's accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the study

The following hypotheses were raised to guide the study

1. There is no significant difference in the means ratings of male and female business education lecturers' preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

2. There is no significant difference in the means ratings of male and female business education lecturers on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Nworgu, (2015) opined is one in which group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people or items considered being representative of the entire group. The total population used for the study comprised of 60 business education lecturers in College of Education, Warri, College of Education Akamkpa and Federal college education, Asaba. The entire population was used for the study because of it manageable sizes no sampling and sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was a researchers constructed questionnaire titled, ‘preparedness and utilization of artificial intelligence on business education learning Questionnaire (PAUOAIQBELQ)’. The questionnaires contain 11 items and was assigned a scale of 4 – point rating of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by two experts, one from curriculum and instruction Department and other from business education Department all from college of Education, Warri. The experts examined the items of the instrument on the basis of items clarity, adequacy, suitability and relevance of items to the objectives of the study. The comment, suggestions and corrections of the validators were used to develop the final copy of the instrument. However, none of the items was dropped. The instrument was subjected to test – retest to ascertain its reliability. To achieve this, 20 copies of the instrument was administered to lecturers in college of education, Mosogar who are not part of the study but share similar characteristics with the sample of the study. The data collected was computed using the Cronbach alpha Statistic which yield 0.74 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Mean and Standard deviation was used to analyse the research questions and mean between 4.00-3.50 (VHE), 3.49-2.50 (HE), 2.49-1.50 (LE) and 1.49-1.00 (VLE). While, t-test was used to test all the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent does the teacher’s preparedness in the use of AI enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of the respondents rating of teachers’ preparedness enhance the teaching of business education courses.

S/N	Question Item	No	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1.	I have been taught the basic concept of AI	60	2.53	1.081	High Extent
2.	As a teacher, I have the ability to use AI tools for teaching	60	2.65	1.022	High Extent
3.	I am fully prepared to trouble shoot issues with AI technology	60	2.75	.914	High Extent
4.	I can evaluate the effectiveness of AI tools in enhancing teaching	60	3.03	.823	V.High Extent
5.	It affords me the opportunity to learn new AI tools for teaching	60	2.87	.1.049	High Extent
6.	I have the confidence in explaining the use of AI in teaching	60	3.02	.813	V. High Extent
	Grand mean		2.80	.050	High Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 revealed that the mean rating of the respondents to items 1, 2,3,5, and 6 respectively indicated high extent. It was also showed that the mean ratings of the respondents to items 4 and 6 respectively indicated very highly extent. The implication was that teachers’ preparedness would highly enhance the use of AI in the teaching of business education courses.

Research Question two

To what extent does the accessibility of AI resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of the respondents rating of teachers ‘accessibility of A.I resources necessary for teaching enhance the teaching of business education courses.

S/N	Question Item	No	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
7.	The school Management provide us adequate access to AI resources	60	2.10	.986	Low Extent
8.	The school provide the necessary technical support for teachers for the use of A.I tools	60	1.92	.962	Low Extent
9.	Internet connection was fully provided in the classroom to support AI activities	60	1.85	.899	Low Extent
10.	Up-to-date relevant resources were made available to us for AI Teaching.	60	1.68	.983	Low Extent
11.	The school management provides sufficient hardware for utilizing AI in the classroom	60	2.25	.985	Low Extent
	Grand mean		2.38	0.963	Low Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 revealed that the mean rating of the respondents to items 7 - 11 respectively indicated low extent. This implied that all the respondents have negative insight on the non-provision of A.I resource and lack of accessibility by teacher will hinder the enhancement of AI in the teaching of business education courses.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Table 3: T- test analysing showing the mean rating of male and female Business Education lecturers’ preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education Courses in College of Education in south -south

Group Statistics								
GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	p-value	Decision	
MALE	20	2.87	.81	.430	58	.669	NSig	
FEMALE	40	2.78	.71					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Since t-statistic is 0.430 with df=58 at p-value 0.669 greater than significant value of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures preparedness in the use of AI enhancing the teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Table 4: T- test analysing showing the mean rating of male and female Business Education lecturers on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in Colleges of Education in South – South Nigeria

Group Statistics								
GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	p-value	Decision	
MALE	20	1.99	1.004	.195	58	.846	NSig	
FEMALE	40	1.95	.751					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Since t-statistic is 0.195 with $df=58$ at p-value 0.846 greater than significant value of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education lectures on the accessibility of AI resources necessary for enhancing and teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Discussion of finding

According to the findings of the instructors' readiness to apply artificial intelligence (AI) in business education classes, every teacher (respondent) was completely prepared to use AI to improve student learning. This was in line with Mateen et al., (2024) Title the role of artificial intelligence in transforming educational practices opportunities, challenges, and implications. The author recommended that AI will enhances students learning experiences by offering them practical and experienced learning opportunities especially when combined with other technologies. The study was also in line with Musa et al., (2022) opined that understanding teachers' readiness and intention towards factors influencing AI in the study was identified.

According to the study's findings, no school has any infrastructure in place to help teachers implement artificial intelligence (AI) to improve instruction and learning. One step guaranteeing the acceptance of AI in schools the school administration's recognition of ignorance as a barrier to AI education facilities. The results regarding the facilities to support the teachers in the use of AI to enhance teaching and learning, the study revealed that no school have any facilities on ground to kick start the AI. The identification of lack of knowledge by the school management as a barrier to AI instructional facilities is a step towards ensuring the adoption in schools.

According to Hypotheses 1 and 2, there is no discernible difference between the mean evaluations of male and female Business Education lecturers about the preparedness and availability of AI resources required for improving and instructing Business Education courses in higher education

Conclusions

From the finding, the teachers interviewed showed that they were generally well-prepared, prepared the groundwork for the use of AI in the teaching and learning in the institutions. But it will continue to provide improvement where is needed. The teachers showed that they are strong enough for the application of AI technology, and also showed that there is still room for improvement in the use AI application.

On the accessibility of resources necessary to enhance teachers teaching and learning of business education courses, no one was available for assessment thereby hindering the teachers' zeal and technical competencies on the use of AI in the institutions.

Recommendations

1. Federal, state and local government and the administrators of higher education should make plan to provide and allowed accessibility of AI resources by lecturers.
2. Federal, state and local government should create awareness to students and lecturers on the use of artificial intelligence through seminar/workshops.

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